

NDAC/LO/084.1

CONVENTIONS AND REFERENCE SYSTEMS USED BY NDAC (REV 1)

This revision of NDAC/LO/084 differs from the original mainly in the following respects:

1. The section on time scales is considerably shortened. A separate note on this subject is anticipated.
2. The centre slit on the main grid has been fixed (in agreement with FAST). It is the 1344th slit counted in the direction in which images move under nominal conditions. As a consequence, the nominal parameters for the starmapper geometry are also fixed (Table 1).
3. The definition of scanfield indices (section 3.4) has been corrected, although the difference compared to NDAC/LO/084 may be practically negligible. A possible doubled transverse index is indicated, eq (7b').
4. The equations for the number of accepted samples (n_{acc}), eqs (11a,b), have been corrected.

Lund 1987 Feb 5

Lennart Lindegren

NDAC/LO/084.1

1986 Oct 10, 1987 Jan 29 (Rev. 1)

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by L Lindegren

IMPORTANT NOTICE:

This paper gives my understanding of some basic definitions, units, and conventions used for the exchange of data between NDAC institutes and between NDAC and other parties of the Hipparcos project. Since a complete understanding and agreement on these matters is essential to our work, I urge all persons concerned with software development and simulation within NDAC to scrutinize this paper and examine your own work in relation to it. Please inform me of any errors or misconceptions that you may discover in this document; if you disagree on some item, or if you have found it necessary to deviate from its conventions. Thank you.

1. Time

The basic time-scale used by NDAC is denoted T and is defined as the number of SI seconds (and fractions thereof) elapsed since the astronomical epoch J1988.0. This is defined as the instant

$$J1988.0 = 1988 \text{ Jan } 1^{\text{d}} 12^{\text{h}} 00^{\text{m}} 00^{\text{s}}.000000 \text{ TDT} \quad (1a)$$

$$= 1988 \text{ Jan } 1^{\text{d}} 11^{\text{h}} 59^{\text{m}} 27^{\text{s}}.816000 \text{ TAI} \quad (1b)$$

$$[= 1988 \text{ Jan } 1^{\text{d}} 11^{\text{h}} 59^{\text{m}} 03^{\text{s}}.816000 \text{ UTC}] \text{ (predicted; TBC)} \quad (1c)$$

The Terrestrial Dynamical Time (TDT, formerly Ephemeris Time) and other astronomical time-scales are explained in The Astronomical Almanac, Section B. !

T has been chosen because it is a uniform, continuous scale closely representing the proper time of a geocentric observer; the unit is the SI second and the origin simply related to the standard astronomical epoch J2000.0.

T will be the independent variable in all ephemerides (sun, earth, minor planets, geocentric satellite, orbital double stars) as well as in the continuous representation of the attitude angles. Frame mid-times, starmapper transit times, set reference times and other observation epochs are expressed directly in T.

The subroutines 'sun' and 'earth' (Lindegren, 1984 June 14, 8) use T as input argument for the barycentric ephemerides of the sun and earth. Ephemerides for the minor planets to be supplied by INCA are expected to be given on the time scale $Y = \text{julian years from J2000.0}$, from which

$$T = 86400 * 365.25 * (Y + 12.0) \quad (2)$$

The relations between T and other time-scales used in the project (by ESOC and FAST) will be the subject of a separate note.

2. Celestial reference systems

The equatorial system defined by the mean equator and equinox of the epoch J2000.0 is used for all object catalogues and ephemerides (including the geocentric satellite orbit) and all internal calculations using celestial coordinates (starmapper updates etc). Input data, such as the satellite ephemeris from ESOC, which is not in this system, must be converted to equatorial J2000 before they are being used. (One exception might be the calculation of transmission delays which is more conveniently done in the system of the mean equinox of date.)

The orbit data provided by ESOC (DDID, 6.7) refer to the mean equator and equinox of date (that is of the reference time of the orbit interval, TREF). Conversion of the rectangular coordinates from this system to the standard J2000 system could use the transformation matrix in Table 2.

3. Instrument systems

Two different systems are used to express the instantaneous position of a stellar image with respect to the Hipparcos instrument: the grid coordinate ($\vec{G}$) and the field coordinates (w, z).

3.1. The grid coordinate

The (smoothed) grid coordinate $\bar{G}$ is defined by the large-scale pattern of slits on the main grid, i.e. after an imaginary removal of all medium and small scale irregularities. (The MSI and SSI are defined in such a way that they do not contain any distortion component that could be represented by a second-degree polynomial in the two coordinates of the grid surface. Thus the separation between large scale distortion and MSI+SSI is unique.) On this 'smoothed' grid, imagine a consecutive numbering of the slits ($n = 1, 2, \dots, 2688$), with n increasing in the direction of image motion for the nominal spin sense. At the instant when the star image is at the centre of slit n (as defined by a maximum of the first modulation harmonic), the grid coordinate is

$$\bar{G} = n - n_c \quad (3)$$

where $n_c = 1344$ is the designated 'centre slit'. (This convention agrees with the FAST origin of the 'ideal grid reference frame'; FAST Calibration Document Version 2, p. I.4.) When the image is not at a slit centre, then $\bar{G}$ is defined by interpolation.

Thus $\bar{G}$ is a continuous, one-dimensional coordinate for the position of a star image with respect to the large-scale slit pattern; it increases from -1343 to $+1344$ as the star image moves across the field (nominal spin sense) and $\bar{G} = 0$ at the centre slit of the main grid.

3.2. The field coordinates

The field coordinates (w, z) and the field index (f) are defined in relation to the instrument coordinate triad [$\underline{x} \ \underline{y} \ \underline{z}$]. This in turn is defined by the projections of the active starmapper and the centre slit of the main grid onto the celestial sphere (Figure 1). Let A, A' be the two projections of the active starmapper apex (see 5.1). The great circle through A and A' is called the instantaneous scanning circle (ISC). Let C, C' be the two projections of the centre slit of the main grid, and O, O' their intersections with the ISC. Then

- (i) $\underline{x}$ is the point on the ISC midway between O and O' ;
- (ii) $\underline{z}$ is the pole of the ISC on the hemisphere containing the sun (so that $\underline{z}$ is about 43° from the sun); and
- (iii) $\underline{y} = \underline{z} \times \underline{x}$ to complete the right-handed triad.

The orientation of $[\underline{x} \ \underline{y} \ \underline{z}]$ in the equatorial J2000 system is given by the attitude (as specified, for instance, by the four angles $\lambda_s, \nu, \xi, \Omega$). Thus, knowing the attitude and the equatorial direction to an object, we may compute its direction cosines with respect to the instrument triad, u_x, u_y, u_z . The field index and field coordinates are then defined as

$$f = \text{sign}(u_y) \quad (4a)$$

$$w = u_y \cos(\frac{1}{2}\gamma_0) - f u_x \sin(\frac{1}{2}\gamma_0) \quad (4b)$$

$$z = u_z \quad (4c)$$

where γ_0 is a fixed, agreed-upon angle close to the actual basic angle (γ). The value of γ_0 (the NDAC conventional basic angle) will be fixed after the first in-orbit calibration of γ , and should then preferably not be changed.

If the satellite spins in the nominal sense (positive about $\underline{z}$), then $f = 1$ for the preceding field and $f = -1$ for the following field. During a FOV passage, the w coordinate of a star image decreases from about $\sin(0.45^\circ)$ to $-\sin(0.45^\circ)$, while z is approximately constant somewhere between the same limits.

3.3. Relation between grid and field coordinates

The transformation from (f, w, z) to $\bar{G}$ is assumed to be of the following form, depending also on the colour of the object (B-V):

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{G} = & g_{10}w + g_{01}z + g_{20}w^2 + g_{11}wz + g_{02}z^2 + \\ & + (h_{00} + h_{10}w + h_{01}z + h_{20}w^2 + h_{11}wz + h_{02}z^2)f + \\ & + \left[(c_{00} + c_{10}w + c_{01}z) + (d_{00} + d_{10}w + d_{01}z)f \right] (B-V - 0.5) \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

The Set Solution should have the capability to determine all transformation coefficients $g_{mn}, h_{mn}, c_{mn}, d_{mn}$, except c_{00} , which may be determined in Step 2/3. (c_{00} cannot be determined on a great circle.) The nominal values of the coefficients are:

$$g_{10} = -(1400 \text{ mm}) / (8.2 \text{ } \mu\text{m}) \simeq -170731.7073 \quad (6a)$$

$$(\text{all other } g_{mn}, h_{mn}, c_{mn}, d_{mn} = 0) \quad (6b)$$

3.4. Scanfield indices

A convention for numbering the scanfields by two integer indices has been proposed by Vaghi (letter of 1985 Nov 12). The longitudinal index IG runs from 1 to 168 in the direction of increasing $\bar{G}$, while the transverse index IH runs from 1 to 46 in the direction opposite to z. For all of our purposes, the large-scale distortion can be neglected when calculating scanfield indices. These can then be expressed directly in terms of (w, z), e.g. as

$$IG = \text{NINT}(0.5*(0.9375 + 168*(1 - w/w_{\max}))) \quad (7a)$$

$$IH = \text{NINT}(0.5*(1.0000 + 46*(1 - z/z_{\max}))) \quad (7b)$$

where NINT() is the nearest-integer function and

$$w_{\max} = 1344 |g_{10}|^{-1} = 0.007872000000 \text{ (nominal)} \quad (8a)$$

$$z_{\max} = (11.04/0.0082) |g_{10}|^{-1} \approx 0.007885714286 \text{ (nominal)} \quad (8b)$$

A finer division in the transverse direction might be used to eliminate part of the MSI+SSI depending on 'scanfield rotation'. For instance, we could use the following doubled transverse index running from 1 to 92:

$$IH2 = \text{NINT}(0.5*(1 + 92*(1 - z/z_{\max}))) \quad (7b')$$

4. IDT signal model

The IDT preprocessing and location estimator produce estimates of the IDT signal parameters β_1 to β_5 , defined by the following expression for the expected number of counts in the ℓ :th IDT sample:

$$E(N_{\ell}) = \beta_1 + \beta_2 \left[\cos(H_{\ell} + \beta_3) + \beta_4 \cos 2(H_{\ell} + \beta_3) + \beta_5 \sin 2(H_{\ell} + \beta_3) \right] \quad (8)$$

Here H_{ℓ} is a reference phase for each sample defined by

$$H_{\ell} = 2\pi \left[\bar{G}_{\ell} - \bar{G}_{\text{frame}} + \Delta G \right] \quad (\text{modulo } 2\pi) \quad (9)$$

with $\bar{G}_\ell$ = (smoothed) grid coordinate of the image at the mid-time of sample ℓ ; $\bar{G}_{\text{frame}}$ = grid coordinate at frame mid-time (= boundary between the 1280th and 1281st sample of the frame); and ΔG = MSI + SSI expressed in units of the slit period. In practice $\bar{G}_\ell - \bar{G}_{\text{frame}}$ may be computed as $(T_\ell - T_{\text{frame}}) \dot{\bar{G}}$, and ΔG may be given as a look-up table versus IG and IH. Note that, for the nominal spin sense, $\dot{\bar{G}} > 0$ and H_ℓ is increasing with time.

From the above definition it follows that $\beta_3/2\pi$ is the fractional part of the smoothed grid coordinate at frame mid-time: $\bar{G}_{\text{frame}} = \beta_3/2\pi + \text{integer}$. β_1 and β_2 are expressed in counts/sample, β_3 in radians, and β_4, β_5 are dimensionless.

The estimation of β_1 to β_5 from the expression above is based on those samples in a frame ($\ell = 1$ to 2560) belonging to a specific star. The observation strategy assigns samples to the different stars in lots of 8 samples, known as 'slots'. The first slot in a frame covers sample $\ell = 1$ to 8, the second slot covers $\ell = 9$ to 16, etc; the 320th and last slot in the frame covers $\ell = 2553$ to 2560. Let $s = 1 + \text{INT}[(\ell-1)/8]$ be a numbering of the slots in a frame, and $s(1), s(2), \dots, s(n)$ the slots assigned to a specific star (where n , the number of slots, is $1 \leq n \leq 320$). The mean slot number of the frame observation of that star is defined as the integer

$$m_{\text{slot}} = \text{INT} \left[\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n s(i) \right] \quad (10)$$

Clearly $1 \leq m_{\text{slot}} \leq 320$. Note that a star observed symmetrically about the frame mid-time will have $m_{\text{slot}} = 160$. The number of accepted samples is normally

$$n_{\text{acc}} = 8n \quad (11a)$$

However, there should be at least the option to skip the first sample on a given star in each interlacing period, in which case we would have

$$n_{\text{acc}} = 8n - n_{\text{ilp}} \quad (11b)$$

where n_{ilp} is the number of interlacing periods containing the star in question ($1 \leq n_{\text{ilp}} \leq 16$; $n_{\text{ilp}} = 16$ for 'fully observable stars').

5. Starmapper signal model

5.1. The starmapper geometry

The nominal layout of the starmappers in relation to the main grid is shown in Figure 2. The two starmappers on either side of the main grid are designated SM1 and SM2 and may be distinguished by an index $h = 1$ (for SM1, $w > 0$) or $h = 2$ (SM2, $w < 0$). Which of the starmappers is actually used ('active') will be specified in the Data Catalogue File (DDID, 5.6, OFF = 80). Each starmapper contains two groups of four slits: the vertical group ($g = 1$) and the chevron group ($g = 2$). The position of a slit group is defined by its *centre line*, i.e. the nominal barycentre of the four slits. The location of each slit centre with respect to the centre line is indicated by the magnified insert in Figure 2 (for $g = 2$ of SM1). The relative positions are the same for the vertical group of SM1, while the signs must be reversed for the vertical and chevron groups of SM2. Thus, the two slits closest together in a group are always on the side facing the main grid.

This definition of the centre line (as the barycentre of the four slits) agrees with the FAST definition (FAST Calibration Document, Version 2, p. I.4.) It is theoretically motivated by a minimization of the transit time error when the scan velocity assumed in the Starmapper Preprocessing is wrong.

The starmapper geometry is described in field coordinates by means of functions

$$w = w_{fgh}^*(z) \quad (12)$$

for all combinations of indices f , g , and h . The following piecewise polynomial representations are believed to suffice:

$$w_{f1h}^*(z) = fh_h + w_{10h} + w_{11h}z + w_{12h}z^2 \quad (g = 1) \quad (13a)$$

$$w_{f2h}^*(z) = fh_h + w_{20h} + \begin{cases} w_{21h}^+z + w_{22h}^+z^2 \\ w_{21h}^-z + w_{22h}^-z^2 \end{cases} \quad (g = 2) \quad (13b)$$

where h_h , w_{10h} , w_{11h} , w_{12h} , w_{20h} , w_{21h}^+ , w_{21h}^- , w_{22h}^+ , w_{22h}^- are effectively constant throughout the mission. The nominal values, calculated from the dimensions in Figure 1 and the nominal focal length of 1400 mm, are displayed in Table 1.

5.2. Signal parameters

The starmapper preprocessing estimates the three parameters A^* , B^* , T^* in the following expression for the expected number of counts in the ℓ :th sample of the starmapper signal:

$$E(N_{\ell}^*) = B^* + A^* S[(T_{\ell} - T^*)\dot{u}] \quad (14)$$

Here, T_{ℓ} is the mid-time of the ℓ :th sample (on the time scale T), $\dot{u}$ is the effective image velocity relative to the group centre line ($u \approx \dot{w}$ for the vertical group, $u \approx \dot{w} \pm \dot{z}$ for the chevron group), and S is a known starmapper response function with origin at the group centre line. Thus, B^* and A^* are expressed in counts/sample and T^* is the transit time across the group centre line expressed on the time scale T . Note that $\dot{u} < 0$ if the satellite spins in the nominal sense (decreasing w).

The group response function S shall be assumed to be a superposition of four identical but displaced 'single-slit response functions', SSR:

$$S(u) = \sum_{i=1}^4 SSR(u - u_i) \quad (15)$$

with the following nominal displacements (Figure 2):

$$\left. \begin{array}{l} u_1 = 0.12415/1400 \\ u_2 = 0.04775/1400 \\ u_3 = -0.06685/1400 \\ u_4 = -0.10505/1400 \end{array} \right\} (h = 1); \quad \left. \begin{array}{l} u_1 = 0.10505/1400 \\ u_2 = 0.06685/1400 \\ u_3 = -0.04775/1400 \\ u_4 = -0.12415/1400 \end{array} \right\} (h = 2) \quad (16)$$

The SSR will depend on the group index (it is wider for the chevron than for the vertical slits) and on the photometric channel (B_T or V_T), and possibly on other effects. It is in general asymmetric, at least for the chevron slits. However, in order that the transit time (T^*) and stellar intensity (A^*) shall be uniquely defined and comparable between the different groups and channels, the following two rules define the origin and amplitude of the SSR:

(i) the origin is located at the median point of the SSR,

$$\int_{-\infty}^0 \text{SSR}(u) du = \int_0^{\infty} \text{SSR}(u) du \quad (17a)$$

(ii) the total area of the SSR equals the nominal slit width,

$$\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \text{SSR}(u) du = 0.0062/1400 \quad (17b)$$

Condition (i) means that the transit time, in case of an asymmetric SSR, is defined by the median of the light curve. (ii) means that A^* equals the stellar count rate (in counts/sample) that would be obtained with an infinitely wide slit.

Separate estimates of B^* , A^* and T^* are obtained for the two channels (B_T and V_T). The final estimate of T^* is obtained by combination of these two estimates or possibly by analysis of the combined signal.

TABLE 1. Nominal parameters for the starmapper geometry [eqn (13)] based on the dimensions in Figure 2 and the nominal focal length 1400 mm.

parameter	SM1 (h = 1)	SM2 (h = 2)
h_h	0.0	0.0
w_{10h}	0.0093756786	-0.0093815357
w_{11h}	0.0	0.0
w_{12h}	0.0	0.0
w_{20h}	0.0154498214	-0.0154556786
w_{21h}^+	-1.0	1.0
w_{21h}^-	1.0	-1.0
w_{22h}^+	0.0	0.0
w_{22h}^-	0.0	0.0

TABLE 2. Conversion of rectangular coordinates from the mean equinox of date to the standard equinox of J2000.0.

Let x_T, y_T, z_T be rectangular equatorial coordinates referred to the mean equinox of the date T. To obtain coordinates $x_{J2000}, y_{J2000}, z_{J2000}$ referred to the mean equinox of the standard epoch J2000.0, perform the matrix multiplication

$$\begin{bmatrix} x_{J2000} \\ y_{J2000} \\ z_{J2000} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} r_{11} & r_{12} & r_{13} \\ r_{21} & r_{22} & r_{23} \\ r_{31} & r_{32} & r_{33} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} x_T \\ y_T \\ z_T \end{bmatrix}$$

where the matrix elements are given as functions of T according to:

$$r_{11} = 0.999\ 997\ 027\ 783 + (1188858 \times t - 118879 \times t^2 + 1 \times t^3) \times 10^{-12}$$

$$r_{21} = 0.002\ 236\ 102\ 257 + (-447206023 \times t - 2974 \times t^2 + 17 \times t^3) \times 10^{-12}$$

$$r_{31} = 0.000\ 971\ 737\ 090 + (-194351169 \times t + 712 \times t^2 + 7 \times t^3) \times 10^{-12}$$

$$r_{12} = -r_{21}$$

$$r_{22} = 0.999\ 997\ 499\ 921 + (999997 \times t - 99992 \times t^2 + 4 \times t^3) \times 10^{-12}$$

$$r_{32} = -0.000\ 001\ 086\ 435 + (434568 \times t - 43455 \times t^2 - 1 \times t^3) \times 10^{-12}$$

$$r_{13} = -r_{31}$$

$$r_{23} = -0.000\ 001\ 086\ 472 + (434591 \times t - 43459 \times t^2 - 1 \times t^3) \times 10^{-12}$$

$$r_{33} = 0.999\ 999\ 527\ 863 + (188858 \times t - 18887 \times t^2 + 2 \times t^3) \times 10^{-12}$$

Here t is the time from J1990.0 in units of 2 julian years (730.5 days),
or

$$t = T/63115200 - 1$$

The expressions are based on Table 5.1-5.2 in *Vectorial Astrometry* (Murray, 1983).

FIGURE 1. Definition of the instantaneous scanning circle (ISC) and the $\underline{x}$ axis of the instrument coordinate triad $[\underline{x} \ \underline{y} \ \underline{z}]$. A, A' = projections of the active starmapper apex; C, C' = projections of the central slit (n_c) of the main grid; O, O' = intersection points on the ISC; $\underline{x}$ = midway between O and O' .

FIGURE 3. The actual starmapper geometry is parametrized by means of pieces of second-degree polynomials $w = w_{fgh}^*(z)$, depending on the field (f), slit group (g), and which starmapper is active ($h = 1$ shown).

FIGURE 2. Nominal grid geometry (derived from the Grid calibration plan, Issue 3, 1985 June 3). The numbers give the nominal coordinates in mm of selected slits on the main grid and of the centre lines on the starmapper. They are measured relative to the symmetry lines (dashed) in the tangential plane of the spherical surface (projection normal to the plane). The magnified portions of the chevron grid give the positions of the starmapper slits relative to the centre line. The directions in which the various coordinates increase are indicated by the compass card. Note that the axes for w , z do not coincide with the lines of symmetry, and that the origin of $\bar{G}$ is at slit number $n_c = 1344$.